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MODERN ECOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE CITY FOR THE URBAN ECOTOURISM DEVELOPMENT

Abstract. *The article studies the ecological framework as a spatial structure, the basis on which the formation of recreational areas for urban ecotourism occurs. The author determines the place and role of recreational areas in the structure of the ecological framework. The article shows importance of recreational areas in the ecological framework, studies the methodology for the design and composition of ecological frames and identifies their main functions. It was revealed that the design of territorial frame systems is carried out based on a comprehensive assessment of the ecotourism potential of the territory. The study of the natural potential of the region is important for determining the areal structures of the tourist and recreational framework of the territory, since urban ecological tourism has a clear focus on its use. The article substantiates the necessity of creating eco-frameworks in city areas, the main functions of which are not only the protection of natural territory, but the development of urban eco-tourism. An analysis of the definitions of the ecological framework presented by various authors was carried out. The advantages of ecological frameworks for recreational areas of the city are revealed.*

Keywords: *urban tourism, ecological framework, protected areas, green architecture, ecological networks, ecological tourism*

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ КАРКАС ГОРОДА КАК ОСНОВА РАЗВИТИЯ ГОРОДСКОГО ЭКОТУРИЗМА

В статье проводится исследование экологического каркаса как пространственной структуры, базиса на котором происходит формирование рекреационных территорий для городского экотуризма. Определяется место и роль рекреационных территорий в структуре экологического каркаса. Раскрыто значение рекреационных территорий в экологическом каркасе. Исследована методика проектирования и состава экологических каркасов, выявлены их основные функции. Выявлено, что проектирование территориальных каркасных систем осуществляется на основе комплексной оценки экотуристического потенциала территории. Изучение природного потенциала региона имеет важное значение для определения ареальных структур туристско-рекреационного каркаса территории, так как городской экологический туризм имеет выраженную ориентацию на его использование. Обосновывается необходимость создания экокаркасов на территориях города, основными функциями которых является не только защита природной территории, но развитие городского экологического туризма. Проведён анализ определённый экологического каркаса, представленный различными авторами. Выявлены преимущества экологических каркасов для рекреационных зон города.

Ключевые слова: городской туризм, экологический каркас, ООПТ, зелёная архитектура, экологические сети, экологический туризм

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Introduction

Urban tourism is a new and promising direction in the tourism travel market; tourists are increasingly striving to visit cities – world tourist centers; in this travel process, a special form of communication is built between the tourist and the outside world. According to D.V. Karandaeva, urban tourism is visiting large populated areas for tourism purposes. D.V. Karandaev groups all cities as tourist centers into centers of cultural, educational, business, event tourism, resorts and centers of medical tourism and centers of pilgrimage [1].

The World Tourism Organization identified this type of tourism as a separate area and, together with Marketing of European Cities and MODUL University Vienna, began developing a joint framework and methodology in 2014 to compare data on city tourism at the global level [2].

Tourism is not only travel, but also production, construction, new jobs, taxes and the country's economy as a whole. The multiplier effect for other industries is obvious, since with the emergence of a point of attraction, related infrastructure and services are created. For example, auto tourism is the construction of roads and roadside infrastructure. As of 2023, in the Russian Federation, the share of tourism in GDP is 2,6%; it is necessary to increase this figure significantly by 2030. There are resources for this, including the ability to create new tools and approaches for tourism development.

A new and promising type of tourism is urban ecological tourism, which is a direction of tourism in which the preservation of natural and natural-anthropogenic elements of the urban environment, management and planning of tourism activities, and environmental education of the population take place [3].

Urban ecological tourism is a relatively new direction of tourism, which involves the preservation of natural and natural-anthropogenic elements of the urban environment, planning and management of tourism activities, achieving several public goals (primarily, environmental education of the population).

Ecotourism, as a promising area, performs a variety of functions that are significant both at the state and regional levels [2]:

- 1) social (preservation of cultural heritage, folk traditions and customs, improvement of the social situation in the region);
- 2) environmental (preservation of regional biodiversity, protection of natural areas, etc.);
- 3) economic (maintenance and development of the regional economy, additional revenues to local budgets).

Within urban areas, the greatest potential for the development of urban ecotourism is the elements of the city's ecological framework [1].

Methods

This paper examined the features of the elements of the ecological framework for the purposes of ecotourism development. The territory scoring method is a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the territory for the development of eco-tourism. The most favorable elements are combined into territorial frameworks.

The frame method allows you to fasten individual parts (countries, regions) into a single whole, and thereby increase their potential. Therefore, when designing tourist and recreational systems, territorial frameworks are the initial basis for defining ecotourism territories and forming their functional zones.

Discussion of the results

In a city, the greatest potential for the development of urban ecotourism may be the elements of the city's ecological framework.

In 1980 V. V. Vladimirov is one of the first to mention the ecological framework. For the territory of industrial cities, where the natural environment is significantly impacted by anthropogenic subsystems, methods, principles and approaches for creating an ecological framework are at the stage of formation.

Currently, there are several terms that are synonymous with the concept of "ecological framework". In foreign literature, the concept of "ecological networks" (econet) is used, which is the basis "Pan-European Strategy for

the Conservation of Biological and Landscape Diversity” (1995). The functional significance of ecological networks is aimed at preserving biodiversity, implying uniform spatial structure of environmental activities [4].

The natural-ecological framework of the city is formed by city parks, forest parks, other large green areas, lakes and reservoirs with coastal areas (planning centers) and linear (ribbon) parks connecting them, river and stream valleys, ravines (natural planning axes).

The natural-ecological framework of the city performs an important ecological function – it ensures the sustainability and interconnectedness of natural elements in an aggressive urban environment. At the same time, it is important to use the potential for self-healing and self-purification of natural complexes. Of no less importance are the sanitation and rehabilitation of ecologically valuable but degraded natural complexes [5].

The ecological framework is a ranking according to the degree of ecological significance of a system of natural areas that are inextricably interconnected, creating the prerequisites for the formation of a natural ecological balance that can maintain the ecological stability of the territory, preventing the loss of diversity and degradation of landscapes. The traditional construction of an ecological framework is based on system of protected areas, represented by a natural landscape, which is a large-area basic reserve that preserves natural complexes, maintains biodiversity, and ensures creating conditions for implementation [6].

On May 13, 2020, the Smart Urban Nature laboratory and the Guild of Landscape Engineers held a round table on the organization of an urban ecological framework. The main problem for discussion was the conflict between theory and practice. A favorable environmental situation and developed green infrastructure in the city are the subject of public consensus. But in the legislation there is no concept of an ecological framework, therefore, when it comes to practice, it is often more profitable to give the land for

construction or a road. The main ecosystem services of the urban ecological framework include mitigation of global climate change; creating conditions for recreation for citizens; creating the cultural identity of the city and its individual districts; reduction of the urban heat island; regulation of rainwater runoff; wind speed regulation; air purification from dust; absorption of carbon dioxide and release of oxygen; maintaining the biodiversity of urban animals and plants [7].

The green infrastructure of the city includes not only parks, boulevards and embankments. These are also green areas of courtyards, schools, hospitals, cemeteries, power lines and other engineering and technical areas, simply undeveloped reserve areas (wastelands). In general, all the green areas that are in the city. Perhaps in Russia this list will soon include green roof areas – a great reserve potential for the city. The concept of “ecological framework” does not exist in urban planning. In urban planning standards there are only “green areas”, “green spaces” and “specially protected natural areas”. If everything is relatively good with protected areas, then with the quality of green areas everything is not so simple. The fact is that the development of specially protected natural areas (sanctuaries, national parks, reserves) is carried out by people with special education – biologists and ecologists. Green spaces in the city are planned by architects and spatial planners. That is, work with the green infrastructure of the city, which is not related to protected areas, is carried out by people who do not have special knowledge of how an integral urban ecological framework should function [8].

Elizarov A. V. grouped sections of the frame in several directions [6]:

- 1) by function – nodes (or cores) and communicative elements;
- 2) at the hierarchical level – frame elements of local, district, regional and interregional significance;
- 3) by legal status – various forms of departmental restrictions on use,

- protective zones, protected areas, new proposed forms of status;
- 4) by ecosystem characteristic – what type of ecosystem the element is represented by;
 - 5) according to the degree of importance of the territory:
 - a) natural territories (steppes, forests, meadows, etc. – everything that has preserved its natural appearance);
 - b) restoration fund (anthropogenic territories (usually arable land), but those in which, in order to recreate a unified infrastructure of the ecological framework, it is necessary to restore the natural environment);
 - c) artificial elements (historically alien to the landscape, but necessary to maintain ecological balance in conditions of intensive economic activity (for example, shelterbelts in the steppe zone).

Vladimirov V. V. in the structure of the natural framework of cities, he distinguishes macro-, meso- and microstructure. The macrostructure includes green areas of the city outside large residential areas, industrial areas, and external transport hubs. Since agglomeration processes lead to the merging of populated areas with each other, the macrostructure of the natural framework of the city in its development tends to make its structure mosaic. Therefore, the formation of elements of the natural frame should go along the line of creating a green zone of the city in the form of water-green diameters, green sanitary protection zones, as well as a system of ecological corridors – green streets, boulevards, protective green spaces, preserved urban river valleys connecting elements of the macrostructure of the natural frame with suburban forest parks and forests. Elements of the mesostructure of the natural framework of the city are gardens, squares, alleys, and other green spaces within residential areas and microdistricts. In the old parts of the city, two types of mesostructure can be distinguished: inter-block (alleys, green streets, squares) and intra-block (gardens, vegetable gardens, front gardens, etc.).

In ecological terms, these types differ quite sharply even with the same building density: in the first case, the anthropogenic pressure is much higher (transport, pedestrians, animals), in the second there are more opportunities for the relatively quiet development of green spaces, their renewal and enrichment. In new microdistricts with a predominantly open plan, despite the growth of green areas, there is a species and structural depletion of green spaces due to the constant and strong anthropogenic impact on the residential area. The microstructure of the natural frame is associated with the peculiarities of the internal structure and the species composition of individual landscaping elements – lawns, flower beds, shrubs, trees. Essentially, this is the development of a natural frame [4].

Ecological framework (ecological infrastructure) V. A. Nikolaev understands it as a set of geosystems within a certain landscape that perform the function of environmental protection and “soft” landscape management. Common frame elements in agricultural, urban, and recreational landscapes are various kinds of green spaces and reservoirs [12].

M. D. Sharygin believes that the formation of an ecological framework involves the inclusion of an already existing network of protected areas, the largest objects (reserves, sanctuaries) of which form the corners (cores) of the framework, and the rest are part of the elements connecting them (axes, corridors). The spatial integration of Specially Protected Natural Areas (SPNA) with the help of corridors and buffer zones leads to increased interactions between them and gives them systemic integrity. As a result, new emergent properties of the system are formed, one of which is the transition from the purely biocentric functional programming of the protected area system to its human orientation. The new environment-forming function of the PA system turns it into a prototype of the EPC, which, thanks to the inclusion of additional elements (parts of territories), begins to fulfill other purposes of the environmental “skeleton” of the region’s space – protects people from the negative impacts of industrial

activities, creates conditions for the population's recreation and the development of internal tourism, preserves historical and cultural heritage, etc. [9].

The evolutionary development of the functional qualities of the elements of the EPC (ecological natural complex) occurs synchronously with the development of the system of protected areas, which progressively "fits" into its structure. New large-area (areal, core areas) elements of the EPC are created within its main linear elements (ecological corridors) or themselves become nodal elements for low-order axes. Giving a territory the status of a protected area inevitably leads to a change (strengthening) of its functional significance in the EIC system [10].

Another option for changing the functional qualities of the territory associated with the formation of a system of protected areas would be the formation of buffer (protection) zones around previously formed reserves.

The ecological framework defines the reserve core and the educational tourism zone. The reserve core is the territory most important for the preservation of the existing ecosystem. Most often this is a large ecological node where the main ecological corridors converge. The elementary components of the frame in most cases have linear forms and can, from the point of view of their spatial organization, be considered as structural axes. Their mutual overlap, intersection, and convergence form the nodes of the frame. Nodal structures are areas of territory with the highest expression of ecological functions for the region, which determine the natural specificity of the region. Structures are usually formed in places of mutual intersection or convergence of linear structures (at the confluence of rivers), or in conditions of high geo-energy potential (island systems, tectonic faults, mountain nodes).

The core of the ecological framework is represented by protected areas, the zone of ecological educational tourism consists of:

- for wildlife – ecological corridors representing the migration routes of animals and their habitats;

- for inanimate – natural monuments – geological, hydrological, etc.

That is, the educational tourism zone consists of linear and point elements of the ecological framework. An example of the influence of point elements of an ecological framework on functional zoning can be found in national parks.

The recreational framework defines the recreational zone – the territory with the highest score, where the areas of concentration of the main objects of tourist attraction are concentrated and the majority of tourist routes are laid. Thus, the design of ecological frames is directly related to the formation of urban ecological tourism.

World practice has developed a basic set of elements of the ecological framework: evenly distributed large city parks; green ring of the city; green wedges connecting the outskirts and the urban center; water-green diameter along rivers. In addition, it is important to create connections between urban and suburban green areas so that animals and birds can move freely [11] (Table 1).

Table 1 – Structure of the urban-ecological framework

<i>meso-level elements</i>		<i>macro level elements</i>	
green ring			
water green arc			
water green diameter			
green wings			

The most important task is to create mechanisms for managing the urban-ecological framework, identifying its links and breaks, giving the identified areas the appropriate status, identifying problematic situations and eliminating the causes of the break of the

frame, identifying and creating conditions for restoring lost links, its connectivity and continuity. The health of urban residents is largely determined by the quality of the urban-ecological framework of the territory. This work requires appropriate legal, economic and governance mechanisms.

Areas of reclamation and restoration of

nature are also often identified. These territories solve the problem of restoring ecological balance on heavily disturbed and degraded lands for their gradual return to the sphere of environmental management as elements of the ecological framework, as well as in areas where traditional types of environmental management are of primary importance (Fig. 1).

SORTIR DU VERT

Fig. 1 – Supporting elements of the urban-ecological framework of Nizhny Novgorod¹

It is advisable to separate the terms natural frame and ecological frame. The natural framework is close in meaning to the system of specially protected natural areas, that is, a set of ecologically and functionally interconnected specially protected natural areas, capable of ensuring the preservation of ecological balance at a level that gives maximum environmental, socio-economic effect.

The ability of a territory to maintain its

ecological balance depends on the functioning of the elements of the natural framework [12]. The most important elements of the natural framework should be territories with a reserve regime, which are completely withdrawn from exploitation and serve as reserves for the gene pool of flora and fauna, as well as a base for monitoring and scientific research.

The ecological framework is a broader concept and, in addition to natural territories,

¹ Source: <https://archiland-design.ru/articles/perspektivy-razvitiya-grado-ekologiceskogo-karkasa-v-niznem-novgorode-48>

includes natural-anthropogenic territories. It is convenient to begin the formation of an ecological framework with the identification natural frame. Hence, it is quite fair to believe that the ecological framework serves as protection for the natural framework from negative anthropogenic impacts. The ecological framework includes all extensively used territories (with a gentle regime of use) of the region. Thus, the ecological framework helps maintain a balance between extensively and intensively (settled areas, industrial zones, transport interchanges, etc.) exploited areas. Natural ecosystems, especially in densely populated regions, perform the function of stabilizing the overall ecological balance and, as it is now called, provide ecosystem services. This concept includes: purification of atmospheric air from pollution; creating conditions for rest and restoration of health; dissipation of surface runoff, prevention of land erosion; protection of the ground layer of air from overheating and mitigation of temperature fluctuations; maintaining the water balance of territories and the hydroregime of reservoirs; protection of biodiversity, curbing the spread of synanthropic species, etc. The main elements of the ecological framework are: nodes of the ecological framework (regional, subregional, local), connectivity zones and buffer zones [10].

Nodes of the ecological framework (regional, subregional, local significance) – territories with the highest environmental value, important for the conservation of all elements of biological and landscape diversity and the development of succession and other natural processes, directly ensuring the maintenance of ecological balance, the preservation of natural complexes and their components; - zones of connectivity (regional, subregional significance) – a connecting link between valuable natural areas, uniting them into single natural complexes capable of self-regulation and long-term existence; - buffer zones (of regional significance) – territories allocated in a 500-meter zone around nodes of the

ecological framework of regional significance in order to reduce the influence of possible negative anthropogenic and natural processes.

In territorial terms, urban ecotourism usually develops in specially created protected natural areas. These are nature reserves, national and natural parks, wildlife sanctuaries, cultural landscapes, natural monuments and others.

Of particular interest among tourists are interesting architectural solutions, which include landscaping on the roofs of houses and even the facades of buildings. Green architecture is one of the most effective and aesthetic ways to improve the microclimate of modern cities. Buildings with vertical landscaping on facades, lawns and rooftop parks, and numerous terraces decorated with a wide variety of plants are increasingly appearing in many countries around the world. Their functional purpose can be anything – from private residences to apartment buildings and hotels, from educational institutions and offices to government buildings. For example, such amazing architectural solutions are: One Central Park, Broadway, Sydney. Architects – Ateliers Jean Nouvel (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – One Central Park, Sydney, Australia²

Urbanized areas around the world have been among the most significant tourist destinations for many years. Until the 1980s,

² Source: <http://www.jeannouvel.com/en/projects/one-central-park/>

tourism research in urban areas was fragmented and not recognized as a distinct scientific field. However, since the 1980s there has been a growing interest in urban studies in general and the field of tourism and recreation in particular. Discussing the role of cities and urban recreation in the structure of tourist activity, one of the most famous researchers of urban tourism, G. J. Ashworth [13] noted that a significant part of tourists traveling both for the purposes of a seaside or resort holiday, and to visit cultural and historical attractions, come to cities (resort cities, large cities with a rich cultural heritage, etc.). The potential of tourism in urbanized areas for the development of urban economies is also evidenced by the fact that recently strategic plans for the development of urban settlements include a section devoted to factors and prospects for tourism development. Foreign researchers pay great attention to the theoretical aspects of the study of tourism in urbanized areas (synonym - urban tourism), in particular, many articles are devoted to identifying the problem area and tasks of tourism research in urbanized areas [13]. A number of authors analyze the impact of tourism on the economy of cities; in recent years, the number of works on the topic of "overtourism" has increased [14], which is very relevant for Russian resort cities in the summer. Creating large green spaces in cities is one of the few ways to preserve the health of the population under the influence of an aggressive urban environment. Green spaces protect health because they can function as restorative spaces, places to support social interaction and physical activity; They are also capable of mitigating the risks of the negative effects of air pollution, noise and abnormally high temperatures. Bosco Verticale (Vertical Forest), Milan, Italy. Architects – Stefano Boeri Architetti is also a unique object for tourist visits (Fig. 3).

As a result of the research, it was revealed that for the construction of specialized frames and further functional zoning urban ecotourism areas require an assessment of

ecotourism resources, which should take into account the main differentiations of tourism: spatial localization and species. The problem of optimizing the spatial organization of tourism is most fully solved by analyzing frame systems. In this case, the ecotourism territory is assessed for the construction of frame systems that have a direct impact on its organization and development. The spatial combination of ecological, recreational, eco-cultural and transport frameworks forms an integral framework of the territorial structure of ecological tourism in the region. Frame systems have areal, linear and point forms of spatial localization, which, when interacting, form cores and nodes of frame systems. These derived structures of frame systems have a decisive influence on the spatial organization and functional zoning of ecotourism territories. Assessment of resources by spatial localization is carried out by identifying areas of concentration of relevant resources, linear structures connecting them, cores of resource concentration and individual point objects. A methodology has been developed for assessing urban areas for the development of urban ecotourism using the frame method: this is a scoring method and a cartographic one.

Fig. 3 – Bosco Verticale, Milan, Italy³

The method of functional zoning of ecotourism territories [11], proposed by the author, consists of the following stages:

- 1) Determination of urban ecotourism territories by identifying areas of territorial frameworks favorable for the develop-

³ Source: <https://ru-architect.livejournal.com/799495.html?>

- ment of specialized types of ecotourism;
- 2) Identification of linear and point spatial structures of territorial frameworks;
 - 3) Determination of derived structures of territorial frameworks (cores and nodes);
 - 4) Identification, using the frame method, of the boundaries of legally established functional zones of protected areas in the ecotourism territory;
 - 5) Drawing up a scheme of functional zoning of the ecotourism territory according to the degree of regulation of urban planning activities based on the allocated legally established functional zones of protected areas.

Cities interested in diversifying their tourism offer should contribute to the formation of both material and intangible factors for the development of urban ecotourism. The first group primarily includes the creation of appropriate infrastructure and maintenance of a high-quality environmental situation. The most important intangible factors include the formation of an active lifestyle for citizens of all ages as the basis of urban culture. The creation of high-quality environmental frameworks and non-standard architectural solutions will contribute to the formation of tourist interest and original tourism products in these territories.

Conclusion

Thus, urban ecological tourism is an unconditional direction for the formation of tourist interest, since the formation of ecological frameworks is not only concern for the environment, but also the formation of a new recreational image of cities. Along with the growing demand for travel services, there is also a differentiation of consumer preferences. Alternative tours to traditional ones are becoming increasingly popular. Urban ecotourism has become one of the most popular types. This is facilitated by the ever-increasing urbanization of the population, as well as environmental degradation in the world. Spending most of his working time behind computer monitors, in cities with high air pollution, with little or no green spaces, city dwellers feel the need to return to the roots of nature. The value of environmentally friendly water, natural and healthy food is realized. Taking these facts into account, as well as analyzing the development trends of the global tourism industry, ecotourism is considered by experts as one of the most promising. The economic effect of such tourism directly contributes to maintaining the well-being of the local population, which receives concrete benefits from preserving the natural site in its proper form.

References

1. Akmalova, A. (2011). *Slovar'-spravochnik po sociologii. Uchebnoe izdanie [Dictionary-reference book on sociology. Educational edition]*. Moscow: Dashkov & C^o. (In Russ.).
2. Nikolskaya, E. Yu., Romanova, M. M., Pasko, O. V., Uspenskaya, M. E., & Saadulaeva, T. A. (2020). Formulation of development strategy for tourism and hospitality industry. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 11(3), 467–474.
3. Zhilenko, V. Y., Amirova, E. F., Lomakin, D. E., Smoktal, N. N., & Khamkhoeva, F. Y. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the global economy and environment. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 12(5/53), 1236-1241. doi: 10.14505//jemt.v12.5(53).08.
4. Vladimirov, V. V. (1980). Aktual'nost' predposylki ekologicheskogo programmirovaniya v rajonnoj planirovke [The relevance of the prerequisites for environmental programming in regional planning]. *Voprosy geografii [Geography questions]*, 113, 109-117. (In Russ.).
5. Evstratenko, A. V. (2021). Voprosy formirovaniya pozitivnoj gorodskoj identichnosti (na primere g. Gomelya) [Issues of forming a positive urban identity (using the example of Gomel)]. *Arhitektura [Architecture]: Collection of scientific cities*, 14, 75-81. (In Russ.).
6. Elizarov, A. V. (1998). Ekologicheskij karkas – strategiya stepnogo prirodopolzovaniya XXI veka [Ecological framework – strategy for steppe environmental management of the 21st century]. *Stepnoj byulleten [Steppe Bulletin]*, 2-4, 11-13. (In Russ.).

7. Shubenkov, M. V., & Shubenkova, M. Yu. (2020). Biotehnosfernyj podhod k proektirovaniyu sovremennyh gradostroitelnyh sistem [Biotechnosphere approach to the design of modern urban planning systems]. *Nauka, obrazovanie i eksperimentalnoe proektirovanie [Science, education and experimental design]: Abstracts of reports of the international scientific and practical conference of teaching staff, young scientists and students*. Moscow: MARChI. (In Russ.).
8. Morozova, G. Yu., & Debelaya, I. D. (2018). Zelenaya infrastruktura kak faktor obespecheniya ustojchivogo razvitiya Habarovska [Green infrastructure as a factor in ensuring sustainable development of Khabarovsk]. *Ekonomika regiona [Regional Economics]*, 14(2), 562-574. doi: 10.17059/2018-2-18. (In Russ.).
9. Sharygin, M. D., Nazarov, N. N., & Subbotina, T. V. (2007). Opornyj karkas ustojchivogo razvitiya regiona (teoreticheskij aspekt) [Supporting framework for sustainable development of the region (theoretical aspect)]. *Geograficheskij vestnik [Geographical Bulletin]*, 1-2, 15-22. (In Russ.).
10. Nikitin, A. V., Mingazova, N. M., & Yupina, G. A. (2010). Problemy formirovaniya ekologo-prirodnogo karkasa urbanizirovannyh territorij (na primere g. Kazani) [Problems of ecological-natural skeleton formation of the urbanized territories (On the example of Kazan)]. *Izvestiya KazGASU [News of the Kazan State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering]*, 2(14), 88-96. (In Russ.).
11. Nefedov, V. A. (2012). *Gorodskoj landshaftnyj dizajn [Urban landscape design]*. St. Petersburg: Lubavitch. (In Russ.).
12. Ponomarev, A. A., Baibakov, E. I., & Rubtsov, V. A. (2012). Ekologicheskij karkas: analiz ponyatij [Ecological framework: analysis of concepts]. *Uchenye zapiski Kazanskogo universiteta. Seriya Estestvennye nauki [Scientific notes of Kazan University. Natural Science Series]*, 154(3), 228-238. (In Russ.).
13. Ashworth, G. J. (1992). Is There an Urban Tourism? *Tourism Recreation Research*, 17(2), 3-8. doi: 10.1080/02508281.1992.11014645.
14. Gianfredi, V., Buffoli, M., Rebecchi, A., Croci R., Oradini-Alacreu, A., Stirparo, G., Marino, A., Odone, A., Capolongo, S., & Signorelli, C. (2021). Association between Urban Green-space and Health: A Systematic Review of Literature. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(10), 5137. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18105137.
15. Tsai, W.-L., Davis, A. J. S., & Jackson, L. E. (2019). Associations between types of greenery along neighborhood roads and weight status in different climates. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 41, 104–117. doi: 10.1016/j.ufug.2019.03.011.